

The spectral species concept in living color

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Abstract

Biodiversity monitoring is an almost inconceivable challenge at the scale of the entire Earth. The current (and soon to be flown) generation of spaceborne and airborne optical sensors (i.e., imaging spectrometers) can collect detailed information at unprecedented spatial, temporal, and spectral resolutions. These new data streams are preceded by a revolution in modelling and analytics that can utilize the richness of these datasets to measure a wide range of plant traits, community composition, and ecosystem functions. At the heart of this framework for monitoring plant biodiversity is the idea of remotely identifying species by making use of the ‘spectral species’ concept. In theory, the spectral species concept can be defined as a species characterized by a unique spectral signature and thus remotely detectable within pixel units of a spectral image. In reality, depending on spatial resolution, pixels may contain several species which renders species-specific assignment of spectral information more challenging. The aim of this paper is to review the spectral species concept and relate it to underlying ecological principles, while also discussing the complexities, challenges and opportunities to apply this concept given current and future scientific advances in remote sensing.

Keywords: airborne sensors; biodiversity; ecoinformatics; hyperspectral images; plant optical types; remote sensing; satellite imagery; vegetation communities.

Plain language summary (PLS)

Biodiversity monitoring based on field data is almost inconceivable at the scale of the entire Earth. Over the past decades, remote sensing has opened possibilities for Earth observation from air and space, allowing us to monitor ecological change, primarily expressed by changes in vegetation cover, distribution and functioning, which can be subsequently linked to drivers of change in space and time, from local to global scale. Recently, the spectral species concept - an algorithm that clusterizes pixels from spectral images with a similar spectral signal (referred to as ‘spectral species’) - has brought attention. The aim of this paper is to review the ecological functioning principles of the spectral species concept and to refine its definition by a better linkage with field observations of plant species distribution data (i.e. presence-absence data) available from vegetation surveys.

108 **Key Points (KP)**

- 109 1. Remote sensing has opened possibilities for Earth observation from air
110 and space, allowing us to monitor ecological change.
- 111 2. Biodiversity monitoring based on field data is almost inconceivable at
112 the scale of the entire Earth.
- 113 3. The spectral species concept, relating field to remotely sensed data,
114 can open new ways to measure diversity from space.

115 1 Background

116 Rapid environmental changes are occurring across the globe at small to
117 large spatial extents due to the combined effects of climate change, land-use
118 changes, and biological invasions (Kreft & Jetz, 2007). Therefore, there is
119 an urgent pressing demand for operational biodiversity monitoring systems
120 that will improve our understanding of the repercussions of these drivers
121 of changes on ecosystem functioning and lead to better ecosystem manage-
122 ment (Skidmore et al., 2021). New approaches are required to obtain timely
123 biodiversity data that are consistently and routinely measured across the
124 Earth surface. Some of these needs are fulfilled by remote sensing informa-
125 tion (Schweiger and Laliberté, 2022). Over the past decades, remote sensing
126 has opened possibilities for Earth observation from air and space, allowing
127 us to monitor ecological change, primarily expressed by changes in vegeta-
128 tion cover, distribution and functioning, which can be subsequently linked
129 to drivers of change in space and time, from local to global scale (Skidmore
130 et al., 2015; Asner et al., 2017). Recent technological advances in remote
131 sensing data acquisition and processing now open new perspectives for moni-
132 toring changes in biodiversity at unprecedented details over large geographic
133 areas, and ultimately over the entire Earth (Luque et al., 2018; Randin et al.,
134 2020). Furthermore, missions like the Surface Biology and Geology (SBG)
135 by NASA (<https://sbg.jpl.nasa.gov/>, Cawse-Nicholson et al., 2021) have
136 been implemented to support the development of algorithms for exploiting
137 spaceborne remotely sensed data and providing a relatively fast but accurate
138 estimate of ecological properties in vast areas over time.

139 Spaceborne and airborne passive optical sensors relying on imaging spec-
140 troscopy (i.e., spectral remote sensing including multispectral and hyperspec-
141 tral imaging) are a good example of the recent remote-sensing revolution in
142 ecology (Kwok, 2018). By measuring information from most of the electro-
143 magnetic spectrum operable for Earth observation, imaging spectroscopy has
144 demonstrated significant capabilities to detect and monitor the spatial dis-
145 tribution of plant communities, species and traits (Asner & Martin, 2008;
146 Schaaf et al., 2013; Schweiger et al., 2017; Skowronek et al., 2017). The pixel
147 reflectance in an optical image results from the integration of multiple inter-
148 actions between light and matter, including vegetation and the surrounding
149 environment (soil, atmosphere). Intrinsic properties of vegetation influenc-
150 ing this remotely sensed information correspond to biophysical and biochem-
151 ical properties (i.e., traits) of leaves and the canopy that can be related to
152 levels of ecological organizations such as ecosystems, communities, species,
153 and potentially to the intraspecific trait of plant genotypes (Madritch et al.,
154 2014; Blonder et al., 2020). Spectroscopy has long been used to capture the

155 characteristic absorption features of biochemical compounds of plants, which
156 biologically corresponds to the phenotypic expression of some of the genes
157 that describe individuals belonging to a given species (e.g., Jacquemoud &
158 Ustin, 2019). These biochemical traits and their dynamics are linked to
159 functional traits, opening access to the monitoring of ecosystem functions,
160 processes and services. Besides, imaging spectroscopy has already demon-
161 strated capabilities for species discrimination in various types of ecosystems
162 (Féret & Asner, 2014; Fassnacht et al., 2016; Skowronek et al., 2017). At the
163 sub-organism level, biochemical properties estimated from observations at
164 leaf and canopy scales (Baret et al., 1994; Kokaly et al., 2009; Ollinger, 2011;
165 Serbin et al., 2012) are described in commonly used radiative transfer mod-
166 els (Jacquemoud et al., 1996; Féret et al., 2008; Torresani et al., 2021). The
167 fine spectral resolution and spectral sampling interval on imaging spectrome-
168 ters provide information to quantify key biochemical properties of vegetation
169 such as leaf pigment (e.g., chlorophylls, carotenoids, anthocyanins), water,
170 cellulose, lignin, nitrogen, phosphorous and protein contents based on their
171 specific light absorption characteristics (Ewald et al., 2018).

172 The link between biochemical properties, functional attributes (morpho-
173 logical, physiological and phenological traits), and taxonomic information is
174 often implicitly assumed when performing spectroscopic analysis for biodi-
175 versity monitoring. Recently, the spectral species concept - an algorithm that
176 clusters pixels from spectral images with a similar spectral signal (referred to
177 as ‘spectral species’) - has brought attention (Féret & Asner, 2014; Rocchini
178 et al., 2021b). However, in reality, the automatic detection of pixel units
179 sharing a similar spectral signature in a remotely-sensed spectral image does
180 not necessarily match with the actual distribution pattern of a given species
181 but may rather reflect the spatial distribution pattern of a group of species
182 sharing similar biochemical properties (Woodcock and Strahler, 1987).

183 The capacity to identify species is often explained by similarities in spec-
184 tral signatures between individuals of the same species, and dissimilarities
185 in spectral signatures between individuals of different species. There is no
186 taxonomic marker in spectroscopy, but individuals of the same species are
187 characterized by a limited set of biophysical and biochemical properties, al-
188 lowing differentiation from individuals from other species. Despite signifi-
189 cant scientific advances, development of automated retrievals of plant bio-
190 chemistry, traits and species identification from satellites across the globe
191 and over time remains aspirational and more work is needed to accomplish
192 this goal, especially for devising a global monitoring of biodiversity change.
193 Here, we aim at introducing the ecological functioning principles of the spec-
194 tral species concept and refining its definition by a better linkage with field
195 observations of plant species distribution data (i.e., presence-absence data)

196 available from vegetation surveys. Finally, we will deeply face complexi-
197 ties, challenges and opportunities associated with the use of this concept
198 for remotely-sensed biodiversity monitoring, including species richness and
199 evenness (alpha-diversity) as well as composition turnover (beta-diversity).

200 **1.1 A constellation of optical sensors to explore the** 201 **spectral domain of the Earth surface**

202 The current generation of Earth observing spaceborne and airborne sensors
203 acquires highly-resolved images over a wide range of wavelengths in the solar
204 (optical) and microwave domains of the electromagnetic spectrum (Ustin &
205 Middleton, 2021). The information measured by optical sensors operating in
206 the visible (380-750 nm) and near to shortwave infrared (750-2500 nm) re-
207 gions largely corresponds to the region of solar reflectance from the Earth's
208 surface, and are acquired for each individual pixel of an image. Image acqui-
209 sition can occur at fine temporal resolutions of days to weeks and in a few
210 cases even at multiple revisits during the day, but data availability and qual-
211 ity are strongly dependent on atmospheric conditions. Optical remote sensing
212 systems include those that measure a few discrete spectral bands (multispec-
213 tral imaging), such as: (i) the Thematic Mapper on USGS Landsat; (ii)
214 MERIS (Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer) on the ESA Envisat;
215 (iii) MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer) on the NASA
216 Terra and Aqua platforms; and more recently (iv) the Sentinel-2 satellites of
217 the ESA Copernicus program. These instruments provide open access data
218 describing the Earth surface at frequent intervals and are complemented by
219 commercial satellites that have high spatial resolution like IKONOS, SPOT,
220 Quickbird, WorldView and more recently the Planet constellation.

221 Some spaceborne sensors provide enhanced spectral capabilities and mea-
222 sure surface reflectance over hundreds of narrow contiguous spectral bands
223 covering the solar radiation spectrum. These hyperspectral satellites are also
224 called imaging spectrometers. The term hyperspectral emphasizes instru-
225 ments measuring a large number of spectral bands while imaging spectrom-
226 eter refers to the type of instrument used, i.e., a spectrometer that measures
227 bands across a spectral wavelength interval (spectrum) and produces a 2D ar-
228 ray of pixels and spectra. Hyperspectral satellites have demonstrated strong
229 potential for characterizing the chemical and physical structure of the Earth
230 surface, with applications in mineralogy, soil sciences, and vegetation sciences
231 (Plaza et al., 2009). Such images reveal details that improve estimates of
232 key vegetation properties and better discriminate between vegetation types,
233 species or even between genotypes of a given species when the spatial and

234 spectral resolutions are sufficient to match individuals (Madritch et al., 2014;
235 Blonder et al., 2020). Several satellites hosting imaging spectrometers were
236 recently launched, and a multitude of satellite missions are in preparation
237 (see the review paper by Ustin & Middleton, 2021). These include DESIS
238 and HISUI on the International Space Station (ISS), the free flying platforms
239 PRISMA and EnMAP (expected launch in 2022), along with NASA’s and
240 ESA’s global monitoring imaging spectrometer missions SBG and CHIME
241 (expected launches in the late 2020s).

242 1.2 Remote sensing tools for monitoring biodiversity

243 Species identification from the measurement of the absorptive and reflective
244 characteristics of plants is based on the hypothesis that individuals from the
245 same species share similar biochemical properties, leading to similar spectral
246 characteristics measured at the pixel scale. However, individuals from the
247 same species may also share similar biochemical properties with individuals
248 from another species which may limit our abilities to assign a given spectral
249 signature to a given species. Besides, one needs to also consider phenological
250 patterns, since remote sensing data is generally only acquired during spe-
251 cific periods of time (e.g. seasonal), or under specific conditions (e.g. health
252 status), or with specific sensor information (e.g. spatial, spectral and ra-
253 diometric resolutions across all wavelengths), all of which may complicate
254 species identification or discrimination. Thus, there are several challenges to
255 identifying a taxonomically identified species with a unique spectral signa-
256 ture. Previous research has shown that minor shifts in plant development
257 induced by the environment and its interaction with different plant geno-
258 types (i.e., phenotypic variability) may result in co-location between vegeta-
259 tive, flowering, fruiting, or senescent stages, each of which expresses different
260 biophysical and biochemical properties. Hence, multiple spectral signatures
261 corresponding to multiple biochemical traits may exist for the same species.
262 Although adding complexity, these problems have solutions. For example,
263 fast growing annual species and facultative annuals (e.g., the invasive Water
264 Hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) are often found in different growth stages
265 and detection requires several spectral signatures to account for the different
266 growth stages that are later combined for mapping the focal species of con-
267 cern (Khanna et al., 2011). Further, spectral discrimination among species is
268 difficult, for example when several species in an ecosystem may share a suite
269 of traits (i.e., strong overlap in the trait space) due to climate constraints and
270 environmental filtering. This happens when trait combinations make individ-
271 ual species phenotypically similar (e.g., grass species in grassland habitats,
272 as shown in diversity studies by Gholizadeh et al., 2019, 2020), or when dif-

273 ferent combinations of traits result in similar spectral signatures (Kokaly et
274 al., 2009; Ollinger, 2011). Additional empirical evidence is thus necessary to
275 contextualize and resolve these questions (Andrew and Ustin, 2008), such as
276 the data provided by field data collections, experimental studies, and model-
277 ing, to achieve full ecological understanding of information from the satellite
278 data to monitor biodiversity.

279 **1.3 From optical types to the spectral species concept**

280 Just as traditional biodiversity theory focuses on differences between individ-
281 uals to assign individuals to different species in order to assess species rich-
282 ness, diversity measured with imaging spectrometer data from spaceborne
283 and airborne optical sensors is based on pixels, each with its own spectral
284 information (i.e., reflectance) (Rocchini et al., 2021a). The term spectral
285 signature is more specific than spectral information and usually applied to a
286 specific type of surface (soil, vegetation, water), to a specific material (i.e.,
287 traits like chlorophyll concentration), or to a specific level of biological or-
288 ganization (genotype, population, species, stand, community, ecosystem).
289 Spectral diversity corresponds to the spatial variation of spectral informa-
290 tion: it is tightly related to the notion of (multivariate) variation among
291 species traits (Rocchini et al., 2018) which is the basis of functional diversity
292 in classical ecological theory. In other terms, spectral diversity reflects - at
293 least to a large extent - diversity in community functioning based on the as-
294 sortment of functional traits in the community, irrespective of the species/in-
295 dividuals that possess these traits (Petchey & Gaston , 2002; Matson et al.,
296 2005). Therefore, spectral diversity is conceptually closer to the notion of
297 functional diversity than to the concept of species or taxonomic diversity.
298 For this reason, it is important to keep in mind that the spectral signature
299 of a given pixel unit in a spectral image cannot directly be assigned to a
300 given individual belonging to a specific taxonomic entity (i.e., the spectral
301 species concept). First of all, the pixel size of the image may not match
302 with an actual individual in the field but may contain several individuals be-
303 longing to the same species (i.e., a population) or several individuals belong
304 to different species (i.e., a community) such that the same species could be
305 involved in different spectral signatures or ‘optical types’ (Figure 1). Addi-
306 tionally, the same suite of biochemical traits (e.g., foliar nutrient contents)
307 may show extremely high spectral variability depending on the health status
308 of the focal plant species such that different optical types could be assigned
309 to the same species depending on its status: healthy vs. stressed (Figure
310 1, panels f,g,h). Hence, prior to defining the spectral species concept, one
311 needs to identify the different optical types occurring within a given spectral

312 image and then assess how each optical type overlaps with the concept of
313 taxonomic species so that one can assign an optical type to a specific species
314 (i.e., the spectral species concept) or a group of species. To confirm that
315 the spatial distribution pattern of pixels sharing a similar spectral signature
316 (i.e., an optical type) can be directly assigned to the spatial distribution pat-
317 tern of individuals from a single species (i.e., the spectral species), one needs
318 ground-truth data on species distribution (i.e., presence-absence data from
319 vegetation surveys) from within the spectral image.

320 Depending on pixel size and size of individuals, pixels can cover multiple
321 individuals or parts of an individual, or stands of one species or mixed stands
322 (Figure 1). In forests, where the spectral species concept was born, a match
323 between spectral and biological species was furthered by the fact that pixels
324 have a higher chance to belong to one species alone (Figure 1, panels a to
325 e, with small pixel size). This does not apply to all situations. Grassland
326 communities, for example, pose a greater challenge because pixels regularly
327 contain several species and optical types can at best be linked to entire
328 communities (Figure 1, panels f to h with any pixel size). These, however,
329 are even less clearly delimited objects than species.

330 **1.4 Spectral species translating spatial distributions of** 331 **optical types into diversity metrics**

332 Various analytical approaches have been developed to take advantage of the
333 spectral information in the optical domain and investigate different dimen-
334 sions of biodiversity (see the review paper by Rocchini et al., 2018). These
335 approaches have demonstrated that it is possible to map and understand
336 functional and taxonomic diversity through space and time, achieved through
337 methodological approaches that differ in their focus, either statistical or
338 process-based. They include data transformation (Rocchini et al., 2017),
339 feature selection and dimensionality reduction (Feilhauer et al., 2011), and
340 machine learning techniques (Kitzes et al., 2021).

341 The number of plant optical types proposed by Ustin & Gamon (2010) is
342 consistent with the Spectral Variation Hypothesis (SVH) (Palmer et al., 2002;
343 Rocchini et al., 2010) which states that ecosystem heterogeneity is associated
344 with high spectral variability. In other words, increased environmental het-
345 erogeneity provides more niches for species to co-occur in geographical space
346 with an expected increase in local species richness (Palmer et al., 2002).
347 For optical types, we therefore expect greater diversity where greater spatial
348 environmental heterogeneity occurs.

349 Spectral species - i.e., the number of spectrally distinct classes that ap-

350 proximate species - are based on the hypothesis that proper processing of
351 images allows discrimination among species, groups of species, or functional
352 groups. Spectral species aim to discretize remotely-sensed information into
353 groups of pixels through unsupervised clustering. The notion of spectral
354 species was successfully applied for mapping tropical biodiversity using air-
355 borne high spatial resolution imaging spectroscopy (Féret & Asner, 2014),
356 under the assumption that the majority of pixels did not contain plant mix-
357 tures and that individual pixels could be assigned to a species, given that
358 spectral variance among pixels meet statistical criteria and that the average
359 tree crown size approximates the pixel size. Underwood et al. (2007) and
360 Thorp et al. (2013) evaluated information content for species mapping from
361 different spatial and spectral resolutions, concluding that high spectral reso-
362 lution contributed substantially more information for species mapping than
363 higher spatial resolution. Hence, spectral species and optical types are con-
364 ceptually equivalent in their purpose to discriminate among optical entities
365 acquired from an image, but the appropriateness of the terminology may
366 vary with the type of ecosystem and spatial resolution of the sensor.

367 A spectral species is then a set of pixels having similar spectral prop-
368 erties that can be used as a proxy for ecologically relevant taxonomic or
369 functional groups, and eventually inventoried to calculate biodiversity met-
370 rics like alpha-diversity (e.g., Shannon's H, Simpson's D, Rényi's H) and
371 beta-diversity (e.g., Bray-Curtis dissimilarity or Rao's quadratic entropy)
372 across a landscape (**Box 1**). Clustering approaches similar to the spectral
373 species framework have been successfully used to map plant species diversity
374 over very different habitats and geographical regions: from African savan-
375 nas (Baldeck et al., 2014) to grasslands in the Platte River ecosystem near
376 Wood River, Nebraska, USA (Gholizadeh et al., 2020), and from the Peru-
377 vian Andes-Amazon tropical forests (Féret & Asner, 2014) to old-growth,
378 secondary and artificial forests of the Shennongjia National Forest Natural
379 Reserve in China (Zhao et al., 2018).

380 Spectral species combined with functional trait estimation contribute to
381 biodiversity understanding by characterizing the morphological (canopy ar-
382 chitecture, gap fraction, etc.) and functional traits, that define the functional
383 role of a species in an ecosystem, e.g. carbon capture strategies by resource
384 acquisition or resource conservation strategies (like drought responses), that
385 then provide a basis to connect spectral species with the taxonomic species
386 that exhibit these trait assemblages. Therefore, spectral species provide a
387 basis to connect with biological species and eventually explore spatial dis-
388 tribution of trait assemblages, their evolution in time, and their linkages to
389 environmental or human factors.

390 2 Complexities and challenges

391 Many of the uncertainties of the spectral species concept apply generally to
392 remotely sensed classified images, which we will not review in detail because
393 they are extensively addressed elsewhere (e.g., Lu & Weng, 2005; Kun et al.,
394 2011). The spectral species method of identifying spectral species with dis-
395 tinctive traits facilitates identification of rare species that occupy few pixels
396 in an image. Rare and endemic plants by definition do not grow in large
397 colonies of many individuals and generally have restricted distributions. But
398 they are of importance to biodiversity mapping because there are far more
399 rare species than frequent species and they are often concentrated in areas
400 of high biodiversity, especially in hotspots (Griggs, 1940; Medail and Quezel,
401 1997; Ricotta et al., 2010). In terms of biodiversity they may represent
402 species with unique morphological features and genetic richness (Myers et
403 al., 2000; Joppa et al., 2011). Other aspects of uncertainty around the oper-
404 ationalization of the spectral species concept are similar to many problems
405 encountered in vegetation classification systems, such as whether rare species
406 are retained in the classified data, whether the classes are realistic in terms
407 of field measured data, and how well the method deals with mixed pixels
408 (multispecies pixels, species with multiple phenotypes).

409 Some of the complications that can make the spectral species concept
410 difficult to handle are shown in the aforementioned Figure 1, where differences
411 in reflection do not necessarily adhere to species boundaries. In fact, several
412 factors determine whether the spectral species concept predicts the current
413 number of species in the area under study. First, more fundamentally it
414 depends on how the taxonomic species are determined, e.g., whether related
415 taxa are characterized by ‘splitting’ or ‘lumping’ criteria, leading to more or
416 fewer species. There are also cases of cryptic diversity, i.e., species that are
417 not morphologically or phenotypically distinct, but having a distinct genetic
418 make-up. Thus, the actual number of detected species approximates the true
419 number. Second, even if species are clearly assigned, the spectral species
420 concept requires the measurement of optically active traits, which may not
421 be the traits that differentiate species, or - because of trade-offs (based on the
422 species functional strategy) or selective pressures (resulting from competition,
423 human use and other types of ecological interactions) - they may be not
424 expressed at the time of measurement. Third, community composition and
425 abundance interact with what is detectable – as the sensor primarily measures
426 top of canopy dominant species, which may identify important ecosystem
427 functions but miss much of the diversity.

428 The spectral species concept, as with most remotely sensed measures, is
429 dependent on the temporal dimension to which it is applied. For instance,

430 measuring the phenological differences among co-occurring plant species through-
431 out the season would improve species detection. Including seasonal changes
432 in the analysis may improve detection of understory species when the decid-
433 uous overstory is dormant. Multitemporal datasets can form multi-seasonal
434 spectral signatures to account for seasonal changes in a species (e.g., Somers
435 & Asner, 2014) and multitemporal spectral libraries are under development
436 (Dudley et al., 2015). The spectral species concept has shown consistency in
437 identifying taxonomic species and traits from other taxonomic species and
438 their traits. Detecting species in mixed pixels depends on the sensor traits
439 listed above and the magnitude of the differences among the spectral signa-
440 tures of the species in the pixel. Species with different functional strategies
441 that are distinguishable in optically active traits will be easier to identify
442 than species with more similar trait assemblies, but which are not optically
443 active. Differences in traits due to leaf types (evergreen or deciduous, needle
444 leaf or broadleaf) create considerable differences in leaf reflectance and timing
445 the date of data acquisition to maximize phenological differences generally
446 always improves the ability to detect sub pixel species. The spectral species
447 concept has yet to be widely tested over the global range of ecosystems and
448 environmental conditions so there is a need to determine its performance and
449 limitations at these scales.

450 **2.1 Ecological issues behind spectral species**

451 The spectral species concept was initially developed to allow computation
452 of diversity indices usually computed from species inventories, but with pix-
453 els used instead of species. It did not intend to directly estimate ‘abso-
454 lute’ species richness from the spectral clustering, but rather hypothesized
455 that relative species richness and higher-level diversity indices integrating
456 richness and abundance or dissimilarity over space, could be estimated and
457 compared within a limited spatial extent corresponding to an airborne imag-
458 ing spectroscopy acquisition. Even in a very unlikely situation of perfect
459 spectral discrimination among species in a remotely sensed acquisition, the
460 predicted number of species may be smaller than the actual species count
461 due to problems related to the potential similarity of traits among multiple
462 species, especially when the growth forms and phenology are similar. The
463 predicted number of species may also be higher than the actual species count
464 if individuals from the same species show phenological shifts. The naming
465 of spectral classes requires matching the taxonomic species information with
466 the spectral information. If the taxonomic naming was based on extreme
467 clumping of groups into fewer taxa or the splitting of taxa into increased
468 number of taxa, the predicted spectral species may differ from the number of

469 biological taxa identified at a site. Perhaps knowledge of the predicted num-
470 ber of spectral species might result in rethinking the criteria for recognition
471 and taxonomic revisions, or similarly knowledge of the species may require
472 rethinking of how spectroscopy data were analyzed.

473 While ecological communities have a variety of either dominant, co-dominant
474 and rare species, the latter contribute a lot to the highest diversity measur-
475 able on Earth. This is a problem for remote sensing approaches based on
476 clustering, as these algorithms often delete clusters with just a few data
477 points (minimum class size or minimum/maximum number of classes may
478 be selected in the setup), thus there is a tendency to lose rare and endemic
479 species likely fundamental for biological diversity and ecosystem functions. A
480 ‘continuous surface’ analytical method that directly addresses this problem
481 is the widely used ‘Multiple Endmember Mixture Model’ (MESMA, Roberts
482 et al., 1998), which models each pixel from a range of ‘endmembers’ (also
483 referred to as ‘pure spectra’) identified statistically from the convex hull of
484 the data hypervolume. The model can retain classes with small numbers of
485 endmembers depending on user criteria but may have the difficulty in as-
486 signing class labels when the variation is continuous (e.g., across a natural
487 continuum or from one habitat type to another, Schmidtlein et al., 2007).

488 Environmental heterogeneity may also affect the accuracy of the spectral
489 species methodology (Schmidtlein & Fassnacht, 2017). Disturbances may
490 increase or decrease biodiversity, with a net zero effect on heterogeneity.
491 There are several examples (e.g., forest gap openings, fire spread, and urban
492 development) that can increase heterogeneity without an increase overall bi-
493 ological diversity. Spectral species should detect these changes as differences
494 in the assemblage and range of traits being measured, although there is un-
495 certainty about the least detectable magnitude of change. Therefore, we
496 expect remotely sensed spectral species to provide a first-order exploratory
497 tool to, at least detect areas that are suspected of hosting a high number
498 of species or, alternatively, identify areas that should host larger numbers of
499 species (based on independent criteria) but don’t. From this point of view,
500 in-situ data would greatly improve the classification, validate its accuracy,
501 and provide a basis to investigate and identify sites that do not match a
502 priori expectations (Foody et al., 2016).

503
504 The R package (`biodivMapR`) dedicated to applications of the spectral
505 species algorithm (Féret and de Boissieu, 2020) on raster data requires the
506 number of spectral species be defined by the user. The method is not in-
507 tended to estimate the absolute number of species from remote sensing, as
508 this problem is highly scale and context dependent as explained earlier. The
509 definition of the optimal number of clusters in a dataset is a specific problem

510 that the spectral species framework was also not intended to solve. Adding
511 a method to determine the number of clusters corresponding to species rich-
512 ness over a full dataset would definitely contribute to the generalization of the
513 spectral species framework over various ecosystems. The number of species
514 included in a remote sensing acquisition is not generally known a priori for
515 most of the Earth’s ecosystems. However, there are statistical approaches
516 to estimate the number with enough accuracy that realistic values could be
517 produced (Chang and Du, 2004; Gholizadeh et al., 2020) , as well as deeply
518 rooted ecological principles based on species dispersal, biogeography, land-
519 scape ecology (Rocchini et al., 2021a).

520 There are questions on whether this method will continue to be successful
521 at the spatial scales of satellites, where multiple species within pixels cause
522 spectral mixing, and under conditions of sparse vegetation where mixed pix-
523 els can include plants, soils, plant litter, geological minerals, water, ice and
524 man-made materials. This will be resolved with the use and applications
525 of the new generation of hyperspectral satellites. The various spaceborne
526 imaging spectrometers (see the review paper by Ustin & Middleton, 2021)
527 that are available now (DESI, EnMAP, HISUI, PRISMA) or in the next few
528 years (e.g., CHARM, EMIT, SBG) all have 30m pixels. These imaging spec-
529 trometers will provide ample opportunities to examine how well the spectral
530 species concept scales up and across ecosystems.

531 In addition to passive optical sensors, reviewed in this manuscript, LiDAR
532 and radar active sensors might complement observations with the capacity
533 to penetrate the uppermost layer of vegetation and provide information on
534 canopy structure, while being less sensitive to atmospheric perturbations
535 than passive optical sensors, Asner et al., 2008; Bergen et al., 2009; Zhao et
536 al., 2018; Mulatu et al., 2019; Simonson et al., 2021; Lenoir et al., in press).
537 For instance, the GEDI LiDAR mission on the ISS is measuring at high
538 vertical and spatial resolutions the distribution and height of global woody
539 vegetation to provide structural information, including understory data, for
540 biodiversity estimates. Besides, the NISAR and Biomass radar missions
541 (launches in 2023) will monitor global patterns of biomass, disturbances,
542 and impacts on biodiversity. Together, advances in the spatial, spectral and
543 temporal dimensions of imagery offer immense data streams that can be har-
544 nessed to better understand the processes of biological functioning, and to
545 systematically map and monitor ecosystem changes from local to regional to
546 global scale.

547 **3 Outlook**

548 In this manuscript we focused on the need to model biodiversity from hy-
549 perspectral remote sensing and field data to calibrate such models. A huge
550 amount of field (free) data is actually available (e.g., sPlotOpen, GBIF), but
551 creativity for mapping species diversity from hyperspectral imagery should be
552 reinforced. From this point of view, the spectral species concept is expected
553 to make a major contribution in mapping and analysis of hyperspectral satel-
554 lite data to produce remote sensing based essential biodiversity variables
555 (RS-EBVs, see Skidmore et al., 2015, 2021). Even if the predicted spectral
556 species do not precisely identify the number and identity of taxonomic species
557 in an image, it will provide a first-order exploratory tool to detect areas of
558 low to high species diversity. Such approaches will require a better under-
559 standing of the range of conditions under which the spectral species concept
560 can operate. In section 2 we highlight some limitations for applications of
561 the concept, but many of these limitations should be seen as new opportu-
562 nities for research. These include, among others, identification of additional
563 spectral characteristics that can be captured and what additional traits, and
564 thus more species will be detected. We are aware that very small absorption
565 features are present in plant spectra and are statistically detectable but we
566 do not know the physical basis of the biochemical/biophysical material that
567 is absorbing this energy, highlighting an important avenue of research for the
568 future. There is an ever-growing number of new traits reported from imaging
569 spectroscopy research, ranging from phenolic and isoprene compounds, non-
570 structural carbohydrates, fiber content (Serbin et al., 2014; Singh et al., 2015;
571 Ely et al., 2019), essential nutrients including potassium, phosphorous, and
572 calcium (Asner et al., 2015; Ely et al., 2019) to RuBP carboxylation (V_{cmax})
573 and regeneration (J_{max}) (Serbin et al., 2012, 2014; Rogers et al., 2017; Wu et
574 al., 2019). Such information is retrieved from measurements enabled by to-
575 day’s imaging spectrometers, which typically have spectral resolutions of 10
576 nanometer (nm) spectral bands cross the solar spectrum for a total of around
577 200-250 bands, some have 3-5nm in the visible-near-infrared wavelengths and
578 5-10nm in the shortwave infrared region. New satellite sensors under devel-
579 opment (Flora on the Flex platform and GeoCarb) are designed to detect
580 chlorophyll fluorescence with 1-3nm narrow bands in the wavelength regions
581 where chlorophyll fluoresces near the oxygen bands.

582 The spectral species concept is based on the principle that the variability
583 in a spectral data cube is sufficient to identify a suite of traits in a pixel. In
584 these cases, pixels are composed of multiple species with an assortment of
585 different traits. The spectral species concept has been broadened to that of
586 “spectranomics”, which is “an approach to conceptually and geographically

587 link plant canopy species and their functional traits to their spectral-optical
588 properties” (Asner & Martin, 2016). Broadening “spectranomics” has bene-
589 fit for biodiversity assessment across different organizational levels, another
590 area in which the spectral species concept could contribute.

591

592 While differences in traits identify different species, they can also describe
593 patterns at different levels of ecological organization: habitat, community,
594 ecosystem. In Ustin & Gamon (2010), the concept of “plant optical types”
595 is based on their spectral attributes, without any direct reference to species
596 or traits. By relating these optical types to specific traits (e.g. leaf and
597 canopy resources allocated to productivity) these optical types acquire the
598 definition of plant functional types. Just as actual plant species change,
599 the spectral species concept must be dynamic and change. As the range
600 of applications increase, the range of spectral patterns will increase (e.g.,
601 including phenological events like mass flowering or senescent states) (Poyry
602 et al., 2018).

603 Understanding the interactions between biodiversity and ecological/envi-
604 ronmental drivers is difficult (Kreft & Jetz, 2007). From this point of view,
605 collecting exploratory remote sensing data on environmental heterogeneity
606 across large geographical extents is relatively simple and combining that in-
607 formation with changing patterns of functional traits could improve species
608 identification, mapping and monitoring of potential diversity hotspots (Skid-
609 more et al., 2015; Asner et al., 2017).

610 As biodiversity research expands to global ecosystems, there are many
611 questions unresolved. Both ecological sciences and Earth observation tech-
612 nologies are still in maturing phases of development. In this paper, we clari-
613 fied the links between the spectral species concept, optical types and optical
614 traits, and their analogy with ecological dimensions including species, func-
615 tional types and functional traits, as well as the mechanistic link between
616 biophysical properties of vegetation and what is usually expressed as spectral
617 signatures, corresponding to species. The relevance of discrete approaches,
618 and their complementarity with continuous approaches was also highlighted.

619 As stressed in this paper, important advances have been made in under-
620 standing how the spectral signature relates to biodiversity and where there
621 is untapped potential to further disentangle these connections. While one
622 should not overestimate the capacity of remote sensing to directly estimate
623 biodiversity from space (Skidmore et al., 2021), remote sensing captures pat-
624 terns of reflected or emitted electromagnetic radiation that are driven by bio-
625 physical and biochemical properties of vegetation (i.e., patterns dependent
626 on the optical properties of plants that are the phenotypic expressions of their
627 fitness strategies). There are a wide range of scientific disciplines that include

628 all ecological subdisciplines from the population to the global biosphere, bi-
629 ology, soils, hydrology, evolution and phylogenetics, optics, mathematics,
630 statistics and informatics and engineering, that are necessary to understand,
631 interpret, refine and improve remote sensing research. To actually develop
632 and verify methods to identify and monitor global patterns of biodiversity, it
633 will truly take “more than a village” but instead an engaged and committed
634 international contingent of scientists, social scientists, citizen scientists, en-
635 gineers, policy makers, land owners, farmers, and more, to shorten the long
636 road ahead.

637 **4 Authors’ contributions**

638 DR, MJS, SLU, JBF and JL led the writing of this manuscript. DR, JBF,
639 GPA, MD, MJS and SS analyzed the data providing the output for the
640 figures of this manuscript. SS conceived and crafted Figure 1. All authors
641 contributed critically to the development of the concept of this manuscript
642 and to the writing of the draft, and they gave final approval for publication.

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925

Figures and boxes

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Figure 1: Some potential scenarios that can happen in optical remote sensing of vegetation canopies. The graph shows sources of variation in the relationship between species and optical types. Plants of different species might belong to different optical types, but many other situations can also be found. Optical types can be related to information of interest (e.g., species or plant traits) or to irrelevant pattern (e.g., shadows, depending on the research question). Scenario (a) represents a stand with individuals of only one single species, with a similar reflectance. In scenario (b) individuals of two species have a similar reflectance; hence they would be grouped in the same spectral species. This is further complicated once mixing individuals belonging to the same taxon but to different optical types (c) or individuals of multiple species belonging to different optical types that do not follow the species boundaries (d). What many would hope for is that plants of different species belong to different optical types, which may happen (e). Finally, the same plant individual can consist of different optical types showing different spectral properties in e.g. young versus old leaves, shadow and light, or differences in health conditions. This intra-individual mixing property will be related to all of the previous cases (f-h). Note that a stand or individual can pass through several of these scenarios in time (intra and interannual variability).

927 **Box 1 - The spectral species algorithm at work**

928 The spectral species concept is grounded in an algorithm which is now ready
929 available under a free and open source R package in GitHub ([https://](https://github.com/jbferet/biodivMapR)
930 github.com/jbferet/biodivMapR) named `biodivMapR` (Féret and de Boissieu,
931 2020), which is able to produce α - and β -diversity maps starting from the
932 detection of spectral species based on the optical properties of vegetation in
933 the field.

934 Starting from a multi- or hyper-spectral image, a spectral transformation
935 like a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is performed to reduce the di-
936 mensionality for further calculations (Figure 2). Based on those principal
937 components explaining most of the variance, k-means clustering is applied to
938 a random set of pixels in order to detect group of pixel with the same spectral
939 reflectance, possibly related to single groups of individuals/canopies in the
940 field that are sharing similar traits and thus that are likely to be phyloge-
941 netically related (spectral species concept). The detection of spectral species
942 is applied backward to the whole map defining a membership probability of
943 each pixel to a certain spectral species, as based on its spectral euclidean
944 distance from the centroid of the previously defined clusters. A single fi-
945 nal spectral species map can be attained by using the maximum probability
946 for each pixel to attain to a certain spectral species. The spectral species
947 map is further divided into elementary spatial units with a higher pixel di-
948 mension (hereafter simply units), in which calculation of α - and β -diversity
949 can be performed, leading to crucial information on both local diversity and
950 turnover. In order to attain α -diversity, Shannon's H' is calculated for each
951 unit, while for β -diversity calculation Bray-Curtis dissimilarity is considered
952 among all the possible pairs of units. The α -diversity map can be shown by
953 directly taking into account Shannon's H' for each unit and reporting it in
954 a final resampled map. Rather, the β -diversity map needs a further step to
955 pass from a distance matrix to a 2D spatial representation, namely the ap-
956 plication of Non metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS), by deciding the
957 final number of reduced dimensions (in this case three in order to compose
958 an RGB image). The final result will be a unitless β -diversity map in which
959 different colours represent differences among species communities in space.

Figure 2: **Box 1 Figure** - The spectral species algorithm phases. The original image was acquired with the CAO AToMS imaging spectrometer during an airborne campaign over the CICRA experimental site (Amazonian Peru) (<https://www.amazonconservation.org/about/mission-vision/cicra-station/>). (a) corresponds to the RGB representation of an imaging spectroscopy subset. A standardized PCA is applied on (a) and a reduced set of components is selected (b), to maximize signal corresponding to biological patterns on forested areas and discard noisy components. Spectral species are defined for each pixel by applying an unsupervised k-means clustering on the spectral space defined by selected components (c). In this phase, a field survey recognition based on in-situ data is crucial to define the number of singular spectral signatures (spectral species) expected. The spectral species map is divided into elementary spatial units and the spectral species inventory is performed for each spatial unit, by further calculating Shannon's H and Bray-Curtis metrics to derive alpha- ((d), ranging here from minima to maxima from black to blue, green and red) and beta-diversity ((e), in which colours represent differences among spectral species) maps, respectively.